

Enhanced Plant Bottom-up Histone Proteomics

Palina Ryzhaya^{1,2,†}, Pavlína Pírek^{1,†}, Radomír Pech¹, Miroslava Karafiátová³, Jan Bartoš³, Zbyněk Zdráhal^{1,2} and Gabriela Lochmanová^{1,2,*}

¹ Mendel Center for Plant Genomics and Proteomics, Central European Institute of Technology, Masaryk University, 625 00 Brno, Czech Republic

² National Centre for Biomolecular Research, Faculty of Science, Masaryk University, 625 00 Brno, Czech Republic

³ Institute of Experimental Botany of the Czech Academy of Sciences, Centre of Plant Structural and Functional Genomics, 779 00 Olomouc, Czech Republic

* Correspondence: gabriela.lochmanova@ceitec.muni.cz

† Equal contribution.

Highlight: Refined plant histone preparation protocols based on chemical labeling improve LC-MS/MS analysis and enable expanded epigenetic profiling of post-translational modifications in maize.

Abstract

The available tools for histone proteoforms characterization are essential for deciphering plant epigenetic mechanisms and their application in biotechnology. Insights into the epigenetic landscape of plant chromatin can be advanced using bottom-up proteomics. Mass spectrometry (MS) analysis of histone peptides relies on careful sample preparation, including chemical derivatization of amine groups prior to MS, to improve their chromatographic behaviour during nanoHPLC separation. Characterizing histones in plant tissues remains especially challenging due to the presence of diverse, species-specific compounds that interfere with MS analysis.

In this study, we evaluated the impact of different protocols for the preparation of histones from *Zea mays* leaves on the quality of mass spectrometry data. We enhanced the MS-based plant histone analysis protocol by combining chemical derivatization using trimethylacetic anhydride with enzymatic digestion with a novel protease, Arg-C Ultra. Further, fluorescence-assisted cell sorting (FACS) has proven effective in isolating pure histone samples without the need for protein purification by precipitation. Proposed workflows produce highly pure histones that are suitable for quantitative analysis of post-translational modifications and variant composition. They thus offer a powerful tool for investigating epigenetic patterns in agriculturally important crops.

Keywords: *Zea mays*; crop plants; histones; post-translational modifications; proteomics; mass spectrometry; histone derivatization; trimethylacetic anhydride.

Introduction

Epigenetic mechanisms play a key role in the regulation of plant growth, development, and adaptation to adverse environmental conditions ¹. A growing number of studies show that modulation of these regulatory processes can contribute to sustainable food production by increasing yield and nutrient content of crops, making epi-breeding a valuable alternative to traditional genetic manipulations (reviewed in ²). Gene expression is closely associated with the specific patterns of histone modifications within a given genomic region. Some histone marks serve as transcription activators (i.e., like H3K4me3, H3K36me3, or H3/H4 acetylation) while others are strongly associated with gene silencing (i.e., H3K27me3 or H3K9me3) ^{3,4}. For instance, the genes responsible for the stature of maize during development are controlled by the ZmHDA108 — a ubiquitously expressed member of the Rpd3/HDA1 histone deacetylase family — which modulates gene expression by altering the acetylation levels of histones H3 and H4 ⁵. Recently, a significant increase in H3K9, H4K5, and H3 acetylation levels accompanied by a decrease in H3K9me2 was reported in the context of heat stress ⁶.

From this perspective, mapping the epigenetic profile of economically important crops is crucial. Although research into epigenetic modifications in plant species will never rival that in animal studies, plant epigenetics is now an attractive topic, with our knowledge increasing rapidly. Pilot species certainly include maize, a versatile, multipurpose crop which is currently the world's leading crop (FAO 2024: <https://openknowledge.fao.org/server/api/core/bitstreams/df90e6cf-4178-4361-97d4-5154a9213877/content>), and is therefore an intensively studied plant model. It is primarily used as animal feed, but is also important as a food crop, ensuring food security worldwide. Despite the growing interest in the epigenetic regulation of maize (reviewed in ⁷), we are still far from deciphering its intricate mechanisms and facing the need for innovative approaches.

Continuing methodological advances in bottom-up proteomics offer new insights into histone epigenetics. Mass spectrometry (MS) analysis delivers a comprehensive quantitative perspective on histone post-translational modifications (PTMs) and sequence variants at the system-level ⁸. The usual pipeline for mammalian histone preparation prior to MS involves acidic extraction of histones followed by protein precipitation to ensure removal of contaminants and a high yield of pure histones. Due to the frequent occurrence of lysine and arginine residues in the amino acid sequence of histones, chemical derivatization of amine groups is performed before trypsin digestion to prevent the formation of short hydrophilic peptides and their loss. Another round of derivatization, usually performed on the peptide level to label newly formed amino-groups, enhances chromatographic separation ⁹. The retention and resolution of labelled peptides on the analytical chromatography column vary depending on the derivatization reagent used. Propionic anhydride (Prop) is the most commonly used agent for mammalian histone derivatization, often complemented by the labeling with phenylisocyanate at the peptide level ¹⁰. The enhanced separation of

frequently occurring isobaric histone modified peptides and their quantification from the MS1 level can be achieved using trimethylacetic anhydride (TMA)¹¹. Recently, protein digestion with the novel proteinase with increased arginine-cleavage specificity, Arg-C Ultra, followed by TMA derivatization at the peptide level, has been shown to facilitate the preparation of mammalian histones¹². Despite the need for further refinement or development of existing methods, LC-MS/MS techniques for mammalian histone preparation and measurement have been widely adopted by the scientific community. These methods are now routinely used to dissect changes in histone PTMs in the context of diseases or medical treatments¹³⁻¹⁵.

Conversely, analyzing plant histones using MS is less straightforward. The complex composition of plant tissues—particularly the presence of diverse secondary metabolites—can interfere with histone preparation, affecting both the purity and yield of the peptide mixture. As a result, histone characterization is less commonly performed in plant studies compared to mammalian research¹⁶.

Previous studies demonstrated that histones from a model plant *Arabidopsis thaliana* are hard to re-dissolve in water after precipitation^{16,17}, and additional methanol:chloroform cleanup of histone proteins originating from *Arabidopsis* leaves is required prior to LC-MS/MS¹⁶. Filter-aided histone preparation procedure coupled with propionylation (FASP-based procedure) established by Ledvinová et al.¹⁷ significantly improved proteomic analysis from as little as 0.5 g of plant tissue, allowing quantification of peptidofoms and determination of the ratio between histone sequence variants in various biological contexts. For instance, comprehensive proteomic characterization of histone PTMs revealed the relationship between phenotypic features and the pattern of histone modifications in *A. thaliana* plants with abolished histone deacetylase activities¹⁸. A distinct H3.1:H3.3 ratio was detected in *Arabidopsis* mutants lacking certain histone chaperones¹⁹. Very recently, using the same approach, the interplay between different epigenetic layers, *i.e.*, changes in histone PTMs and replacement of histone sequence variants, was demonstrated^{20,21}. Specifically, it was shown that defects in histone chaperone function (*e.g.*, chromatin assembly factor-1 or nucleosome assembly protein 1 mutations) translate into an altered epigenetic landscape, which aids the plant in mitigating internal instability²¹. Here, the FASP-based procedure even enabled the discrimination and quantification of the subtypes of histone sequence variants H2A.Z (H2A.Z.8, H2A.Z.9, and H2A.Z.11), H2A.X (H2A.X.3 and H2A.X.5), and H2A.W (H2A.W.6 and H2A.W.7). Another study revealed that histone variant replacement plays a substantial role in chromatin remodeling during callus induction and propagation, while changes in histone acetylation and methylation levels serve as fine-tuning mechanisms important for the activation or repression of specific genes²⁰. While the FASP-based plant histone preparation protocol is effective, it yields fewer identified post-translationally modified peptidofoms due to the low hydrophobicity of the propionyl adduct and insufficient resolution of isobaric peptides.

In pursuit of more precise histone profiling in plants, we present MS-based methods that enhance the quantitative analysis of histone peptidofoms and facilitate new discoveries in plant epigenetics. To align the quality of plant histone characterization—specifically the range of quantified peptidofoms—with that achieved in mammalian systems, we incorporated chemical derivatization using TMA into the histone preparation workflow for *Zea mays* leaves. Nuclei purified via flow cytometry were tested as an alternative input to minimize interference from natural plant compounds. Of the seven protocol variants tested, we selected two efficient methods for preparing maize histones for LC-MS/MS analysis. In the first case, the extracted histones are precipitated, followed by enzymatic cleavage using Arg-C Ultra, and the peptides are chemically derivatized using TMA. The FACS-based protocol yields pure histones, allowing direct cleavage of proteins in solution followed by TMA labelling. It is advantageous for plants in which the chemical composition of the tissue interferes with any step in the histone sample preparation procedure or subsequent LC-MS/MS measurement. Both protocols provide comprehensive quantitative data on histone marks, offering a basis for analysis of epigenetic regulations in maize.

Materials and methods

Altogether, seven protocols were tested for plant histone preparation (Fig. 1). Below, common procedures shared across multiple protocols are described, and protocol-specific steps are detailed within each relevant section. Protocols 5 and 3S, which were evaluated in the study as the preferred methods for histone preparation from maize and other crops, have been deposited in the step-by-step format to Zenodo with DOI 10.5281/zenodo.15877728.

Material for histone preparation

Phenylmethylsulfonyl fluoride (PMSF) was purchased from Thermo Fisher Scientific (MA, USA). Ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA) and the Bradford assay were purchased from Bio-Rad (CA, USA). Triton X-100 was purchased from Carl Roth (Germany). Sulfuric and hydrochloric acids were purchased from Penta (Czech Republic). Acetonitrile (ACN) and formic acid (FA) were purchased from Honeywell (NC, USA). Trimethylacetic anhydride (TMA), Propionic anhydride (Prop), trichloroacetic acid (TCA), ammonium bicarbonate (AB), SOLu-Trypsin Dimethylated and dithiothreitol (DTT) were purchased from Merck (Germany). AttractSPE® Tips C18 were purchased from Affinisep (France). Arg-C Ultra was purchased from Promega (WI, USA). Percoll, protease inhibitor cocktail P9599, and phosphatase inhibitor cocktail P5726 were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (Germany).

Plant material

The maize seeds of *Zea mays* inbred line B73 used in the study were harvested at the Institute of Experimental Botany in the Czech Republic. The leaves for nuclei isolation were collected from 16-day-old plantlets. The

plants were grown in the soil under controlled conditions in growing chambers with a 14-hour period of daylight at 24°C and 20°C at night.

Isolation of crude nuclei (applied in protocols 1, 2, 3, 4, and 5)

Crude nuclei were isolated according to a previously published protocol¹⁷. The leaves of *Zea mays* plantlets were ground in liquid nitrogen and homogenized in extraction buffer containing 10mM NaCl, 10mM 2-(N-morpholino)ethanesulfonate (pH 6.0), 5mM EDTA, 0.25M sucrose, 0.6% Triton X-100, 0.2M spermidine, 100mM PMSF, 45mM sodium butyrate, and 20 mM β -mercaptoethanol. The homogenate was filtered through nylon mesh (pore size of 162 μ m) and centrifuged at 3000 \times g at 4 °C for 10 minutes. The resulting pellet was washed twice with extraction buffer, resuspended in Percoll buffer (2.4 g of 5 \times concentrated extraction buffer and 18 g of Percoll from Sigma-Aldrich), and centrifuged at 4000 \times g at 4 °C for 15 minutes. Nuclei floating at the surface of the Percoll buffer were collected. Nuclei were washed three times in wash buffer (75mM NaCl, 10mM EDTA, 50mM Tris-HCl pH 8.0), and centrifuged at 3000 \times g at 4 °C for 10 min. The pellet was incubated in histone lysis buffer (80mM NaCl, 20mM EDTA, 1% Triton X-100) supplemented with protease, deacetylase, and phosphatase inhibitors (0.1mM PMSF, 45mM sodium butyrate, and 10 μ L/mL protease inhibitor cocktail (P9599) and 10 μ L/mL phosphatase inhibitor cocktail (P5726) for 1 h on ice, spun at 10,000 \times g for 5 min, washed with 50mM Tris-HCl 200 μ L, and spun at 10,000 \times g for 5 min. Histones were extracted from the chromatin pellet into 250 μ L of ice-cold 0.2M H₂SO₄ overnight at 4 °C.

FACS-assisted nuclei isolation (applied in protocols 3S and 4S)

Alternatively, maize nuclei were purified using a flow cytometer FACSAria SORP (BD Biosciences, San Jose, CA, USA) as published previously²². Briefly, maize leaves were fixed for 20 min at 4°C in 2% formaldehyde made in Tris buffer (10mM Tris-HCl, 10mM EDTA, 100mM NaCl, pH 7.5) and washed three times in Tris buffer. The nuclei were released by chopping the leaves with a razor blade in ice-cold LB01 lysis buffer. The crude nuclei suspension was filtered through a 50- μ m nylon mesh, stained with DAPI (2 μ g/mL), and analysed. In total, 27 batches of 1,000,000 G1 nuclei each were collected on ice into the 2.0 mL microtubes containing 10 μ L of ddH₂O. Isolated nuclei were immediately centrifuged at 3,000 \times g for 5 min to remove the sheath fluid. Subsequently, 50 μ L of 0.2M H₂SO₄ was added to the pellet for lysis and histone extraction. Samples were incubated overnight on a rotator at 4 °C. After centrifugation at 16,100 \times g for 8 minutes, the supernatant containing histones was transferred to a new vial, and the samples were stored at -80 °C.

Protein concentration measurement

Protein concentration was measured using the Micro BCA™ Protein Assay Kit in a microplate. One μ L of histone extract in sulfuric acid was diluted 50 times with water, and 50 μ L of WR reagent was added. After 2h incubation at 37 °C, the absorbance was measured at 562 nm in Biotek Synergy H1 microplate reader (Agilent Technologies, CA, USA).

Histone precipitation (applied in protocols 4, 4S, and 5)

250 μ L of histone extract was precipitated with 250 μ L of 50% ice-cold trichloroacetic acid by incubation with shaking at 0 °C for 30 min. The precipitate was collected by centrifugation at 5,000 \times g and 4 °C for 30 min, washed with 50mM HCl in acetone, twice with pure acetone, and dried at room temperature.

Protocol 1: Filter-aided histone preparation from crude nuclei coupled with trypsin digestion and propionylation

Sixteen μ g of histone extract in sulfuric acid was subjected to chemical derivatization. First, pH was adjusted to 8 with NH_4OH . Derivatization reagent was freshly prepared for each reaction by mixing propionic anhydride with ACN in 1:3 (v/v) ratio. Samples were incubated at 37°C for 20 min, 750rpm, and then concentrated in a vacuum concentrator to 5 μ L at 35 °C for 50 min. Then, the samples were diluted with 50% ACN to a final volume of 20 μ L, and again, the pH was adjusted to 8, and the second round of chemical derivatization was performed. Following clean-up and enzymatic digestion using the filter-aided sample preparation described below, newly released peptide N-termini were subjected to the above-described chemical derivatization, with the addition of 5 μ L of propionylation reagent. Then, the samples were concentrated in a vacuum concentrator to dryness at 35 °C overnight.

Protocol 2: Filter-aided histone preparation from crude nuclei coupled with trypsin digestion and TMA-labelling

Sixteen μ g of histone extract in sulfuric acid was subjected to chemical derivatization. First, pH was adjusted to 8 with NH_4OH . For the protein-level TMA derivatization described below, 3 μ l of reagent were used. Following clean-up and enzymatic digestion using the filter-aided sample preparation, newly released peptide N-termini were subjected to peptide-level TMA derivatization as described below.

Protocol 3 and 3S: Histone preparation coupled with in-solution trypsin digestion and TMA-labelling

The pH of histones extracted from crude (protocol 3) or sorted nuclei (protocol 3S) was adjusted to 8 with NH_4OH , and the volume was reduced to 20 μ L. For the protein-level derivatization described below, 3 μ l of TMA reagent were used. The resulting labeled protein sample was concentrated to 5 μ L, and 0.25 g of SOLu-trypsin in 40 μ L of 100mM AB was added. After 4 h of incubation at 37 °C, another aliquot of 0.25 μ g of SOLu-trypsin was added, and the sample was then incubated for further 12 h at 37 °C. Newly released peptide N-termini were subjected to the peptide-level TMA derivatization as described below.

Protocol 4 and 4S: Histone preparation including protein precipitation, digestion with trypsin, and TMA-labelling

Precipitated histones from crude (protocol 4) or sorted nuclei (protocol 4S) were re-dissolved in 20 μ L of water. For the protein-level derivatization described below, 3 μ L of TMA reagent were used. The resulting labeled protein sample was concentrated to 5 μ L, and 0.25 μ g of SOLu-trypsin in 40 μ L of 100mM AB was added. After 4 h of incubation at 37 °C, another aliquot of 0.25 μ g of SOLu-trypsin was added, and the sample was incubated for further 12 h at 37 °C. Newly released peptide N-termini were subjected to peptide-level TMA derivatization as described below.

Protocol 5: Histone preparation from crude nuclei including protein precipitation, digestion with Arg-C Ultra, and TMA-labelling

Precipitated histones were re-dissolved in 27 μ L of water. 0.5M AB (pH 7.5) and 200mM DTT were added to a final concentration of 50 mM and 10 mM, respectively. 0.1 μ g of Arg-C Ultra was added, the mixture was incubated at 37 °C, and after 90min incubation, the same amount of Arg-C Ultra was added, followed by another 90min incubation. Ten μ L of 100% (v/v) ACN was added to the sample. The pH was adjusted to 8 with NH_4OH . For the peptide-level derivatization described below, 2.25 μ L of TMA reagent was added to each sample.

Filter-aided histone preparation (applied in protocols 1 and 2)

Protein-level derivatized samples were diluted with 300 μ L of 8M urea in 0.1M Tris-HCl (pH 8.5), placed in YM-10 Microcon filter unit, centrifuged 14,000 \times g at 20 °C for 30 min, and washed twice with 200 μ L of 8M urea and three times with 100 μ L of 100mM AB. Then, 50 μ L of 100mM AB was added with 400 ng of SOLu-Trypsin Dimethylated and incubated at 37 °C overnight. The samples were spun at 14,000 \times g for 10 min three times, the second and third time with the addition of 50 μ L of 100mM AB. The samples were concentrated in a vacuum concentrator to 20 μ L at 37 °C.

Chemical derivatization of histones using trimethylacetic anhydride

TMA derivatization reagent was prepared by mixing trimethylacetic anhydride with ACN in 1:3 (v/v) ratio. The reagent was prepared fresh for each reaction.

For protein-level derivatization (applied in protocols 2, 3, 3S, 4, and 4S), the samples were incubated with the reagent for 5 h at room temperature while shaking, followed by a repeated derivatization step including 16 h incubation, and then subjected to two rounds of microwave-assisted derivatization. The sample volume was reduced in a vacuum concentrator to approximately 5 μ L, then diluted with 50% (v/v) ACN to a final volume of 12 μ L. The sample was incubated in a microwave oven for the first round of microwave-assisted derivatization. This consisted of three subcycles with the following steps: adjustment of the sample's pH to 8

with NH_4OH , addition of 3 μL of TMA reagent, and two 1-min incubations in the microwave oven at 350 W with a short centrifugation between them. The sample was then concentrated to 3-5 μL at 35 °C, 20 μL of 50% ACN was added, and the second round of microwave-assisted derivatization was carried out with the same protocol. The resulting TMA-derivatized protein sample was concentrated to 5 μL .

Two rounds of peptide-level derivatization were performed following digestion of either derivatized proteins with trypsin (protocols 2, 3, 3S, 4, and 4S) or non-derivatized proteins with Arg-C Ultra (protocol 5), using the above-described microwave-assisted derivatization protocol with the addition of 5 μL of TMA reagent. Then, the samples were dried in a vacuum concentrator at 35 °C overnight.

Sample desalting (applied in all protocols)

The dried samples were reconstituted in 50 μL of 0.1% trifluoroacetic acid (TFA). Desalting was performed using AttractSPE® Tips C18. Peptides were sequentially eluted with 2 \times 10 μL of 0.1% TFA in 50% ACN and 2 \times 20 μL of 0.1% TFA in 75% ACN. The eluates were transferred to an LC vial, concentrated to 10 μL , and acidified with FA to a final concentration of 1 %.

LC-MS/MS analysis

The samples were analyzed in a random order using an Ultimate 3000 RSLCnano liquid chromatograph coupled to an Orbitrap Fusion Lumos Tribrid mass spectrometer (Thermo Fisher Scientific). The amount of 200 ng of each peptide mixture was injected, concentrated on an online trap column (cartridge type $\mu\text{Precolumn}$, 300 μm ID, 5 mm long, Thermo Fisher Scientific) packed with C18 PepMap100 (5 μm particles, 100 Å), and separated on an Aurora C18 analytical column (25 cm long, 75 μm inner diameter, 1.7 μm particles; Ion Opticks, Australia). Trap and analytical columns were tempered at 25 °C and at 50 °C, respectively. The mobile phases used for the gradient elution consisted of a binary mixture of 0.1% FA in water (A) and 0.1% FA in 80% ACN (B). Peptides were eluted with a 120min gradient at a 300 $\text{nL}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$ flow rate and the content of B rising from 3 % (0–4 min), 3 to 42 % (4–107 min), 42 to 80 % (107–115 min), and followed by an isocratic wash of 80 % B (115–120 min). Before sample injection into the loop, the trapping and analytical columns were equilibrated with 99:1 (mobile phase A:B) at a 400 nL/min flow rate. The analytical column outlet was directly connected to the Digital PicoView 550 ion source equipped with Active Background Ion Reduction Device (ESI Source Solutions, MA, USA).

Mass spectra were acquired in data-dependent acquisition (DDA) mode using 350 to 2000 m/z survey scans at a resolution of 120,000 (at m/z 200) with an automatic gain control target setting of 4×10^5 and a maximum injection time of 500 ms. Precursors with charge states from 2+ to 7+ and intensity above 1×10^4 were subjected to higher energy collisional dissociation fragmentation with a normalized collision energy of 30 %. Once fragmented, precursors were excluded for 30 s before the next fragmentation. Precursors were isolated by quadrupole with a 1.2 m/z isolation window. Tandem mass spectra were obtained using 30,000 resolution

(at m/z 200). Ions were accumulated for a target value of 5×10^4 or 500 ms injection time. The cycle time between master scans was 2.5 s.

Database search, data evaluation, and statistical analysis

Mass spectrometry raw data were searched against the modified cRAP contamination database (based on <http://www.thegpm.org/crap/>; 112 sequences), an in-house histone Zea mays database (v230721; 229 protein sequences generated from UniProt), and the UniProt KB Zea mays database (v231108; taxon ID: 4577; 39,228 sequences). The searches were conducted using the in-house Mascot search engine (v2.6.2; Matrix Science, MA, USA) via Proteome Discoverer software (v2.2.0.388). The mass error tolerance for precursor ions was set at 10 ppm for cRAP and 7 ppm for Zea mays database searches. For MS/MS fragment ions, the tolerances were 0.05 Da for the cRAP and 0.03 Da for Zea mays databases. Enzyme specificity was configured to semi-Arg-C, allowing for two missed cleavages across all databases. Variable modifications for each database were as follows: cRAP – deamidation (N and Q), oxidation (M), and propionylation or trimethylacetylation (peptide N-terminal region, K, S, T, and Y); Histone Zea mays – acetylation (protein N-terminal region and K), phosphorylation (S, T), methylation (K, R), dimethylation (K), trimethylation (K), and trimethylacetylation or propionylation (peptide N-terminal region, K, S, T, and Y); UniProt KB Zea mays database – acetylation (protein N-terminal region), trimethylacetylation or propionylation (peptide N-terminal region, K, S, T, and Y). Peptides identified using the in-house Zea mays histone database were refined by fixed-value peptide-spectrum match validator ($\Delta C_n < 0.05$), followed by filtering highly confident peptides using Mascot parameters set to Rank 1, expectation value < 0.01 , and ion score ≥ 30 . Peptides identified using the UniProt KB Zea mays database were refined by Percolator ($C_n < 0.05$, false discovery rate < 0.01). Selected identified peptides were manually inspected, and their quantities were determined and manually validated using Skyline-daily software (24.1.1.202; University of Washington) based on peak areas in extracted ion chromatograms (EICs), including identification alignment across the raw files based on retention time and m/z . The quantitative evaluation of histone peptides was performed in the KNIME Analytics Platform with R scripts. The precursor peak areas of histone peptidofoms were log₂ transformed. The relative abundances of histone peptidofoms were calculated as the ratio of individual EIC precursor peak area to the sum of the EIC areas of all forms of the respective peptide sequence. Peak areas for all forms were treated as compositions and combined using geometric means.

Results

Advancing the understanding of plant histone epigenetics necessitates the implementation and adaptation of existing mass spectrometry-based methodologies. To enhance the detection and quantification of a wide range of histone peptidofoms, we introduced chemical derivatization with TMA into plant histone preparation protocols. TMA labelling performance for plant histones was examined using histone extract prepared from maize nuclei isolated from leaves using a Percoll gradient or FACS. Altogether, we compared

the results of seven histone preparation protocols. Filter-aided histone preparation from crude nuclei coupled with Prop- or TMA-labelling (Protocols 1 and 2), extraction of histones from crude or sorted nuclei followed by in-solution TMA-labelling (Protocols 3 and 3S), and precipitation of histones from crude or sorted nuclei followed by in-solution TMA-labelling (Protocols 4 and 4S) involved derivatization at the protein level prior to tryptic digestion. In contrast, a protocol that omitted protein-level derivatization involved precipitation of histones from crude nuclei, followed by Arg-C Ultra digestion and TMA-labelling (Protocol 5); Fig. 1. Protocol 1 served as a standard procedure currently used for plant histone preparation¹⁷.

Fig. 1. Protocol settings. Histones were enriched by acidic extraction from crude (1-5) or sorted nuclei (3S and 4S). The subsequent steps used in particular histone preparation protocols are indicated.

dT – tryptic digestion; *dArg-C Ultra* – digestion with Arg-C Ultra

Quality control of histone extract: SDS-PAGE

Protein yields were determined in histone extracts obtained from a single 16-day-old plant. The median total protein amounts from biological replicates were 10 µg (crude) and 14 µg (sorted) in neutralized histone samples, and 2 µg (crude) and 6 µg (sorted) in precipitated histone samples.

Prior to chemical derivatization, the quality of histone extracts was checked on 15% SDS-PAGE (Fig. 2). While the separation of proteins in neutralized histone extracts obtained from crude nuclei was impaired due to the natural impurities present in the plant tissues, higher-quality separation of proteins was achieved when isolated from pure sorted nuclei, mainly with a precipitation step included.

Fig. 2. Quality control of histones extracted from crude or sorted nuclei. Histone proteins are found in the region of 10 – 20 kDa. 15% SDS-PAGE; each condition was loaded in triplicate (1-3). MW – MW markers, H – mixture of histone standards. Precipitation – histones extracted into sulfuric acid followed by precipitation with TCA; In solution – histones extracted into sulfuric acid followed by neutralization.

Selection of histone preparation protocols with the highest potential for quality data gain

The mass spectrometry data obtained from individual protocols were compared in terms of the number of identified histone sequence variants and post-translationally modified forms of selected variants. All protocols resulted in a high number of identified sequence variants. Notably, 16 H3 variants, 33 H4 variants, and 62 H2A variants were consistently detected across all protocols. We used the resulting data to map maize variants of histones H2A, H3, and H4, including the similarity in amino acid sequences (Supplementary Table S1). The same portfolio of histone H3 and H4 variants was detected by all the protocols. Slight differences were observed within the H2A group, which exhibits the highest level of diversity (Supplementary Table S1). The analysis of H2B variants was not the objective of this study, since the presented protocols are not suitable for analyzing chemically labeled long Arg-C-like N-terminal H2B peptides, as was previously reported^{11,12}.

Next, we calculated the number of identified peptidoforms of histones H3.1, H3.3, and H4 (UniProt accession numbers A0A3L6GA61, A0A8J8YK56, and A0A3L6FBC4, respectively; Fig. 3A).

Altogether, 31 peptidoforms were identified using protocol 1. The simple substitution of Prop for TMA in the FASP-based procedure (protocol 2) reduced the number of identified forms to 22, which, together with lower precursor peak intensities, indicated a loss of TMA-labelled peptides during sample cleanup on the filter unit. In-solution procedure (protocol 3) yielded 37 histone forms but also introduced a polymeric contaminant, as observed in the total ion chromatogram of the QC analysis (Supplementary Fig. S1). The increase in the number of peptidoforms reflected higher resolution of positional isomers in chromatographic separation, mainly those originating from histone H4 (Fig. 3B). On the other hand, fewer forms of H3.1 K27–R40 and H3.3 K27–R40

peptides were detected compared to protocol 1. Subsequent cleanup of the peptide mixture using single-pot solid-phase-enhanced peptide sample preparation on carboxylate-modified paramagnetic beads (termed SP2)²³ removed the contaminant but resulted in either the loss or reduced intensities of certain precursor peaks, more than 20-fold compared to the intensities before SP2. Purified samples showed the highest variability in the standard deviation of precursor peak areas within replicates, indicating reduced reproducibility (Fig. 3C).

The sample purity was improved in protocol 4 by adding a precipitation step prior to the derivatization, leading to an increase in the overall number of identified peptidofoms to 47. Compared to protocols 1-3, K4 occurring in a short H3 T3–R8 peptide was identified in different modified forms, including K4ac, K4me1, K4me2, and K4me3.

Replacing trypsin with newly released proteinase Arg-C Ultra allowed us to substantially simplify the protocol by omitting the protein-level derivatization step (protocol 5). This increased the number of identified peptidofoms to 54, reflecting mainly the identification of low-abundant post-translationally modified forms of H3.1 K27–R40 and H3.3 K27–R40.

In parallel, we tested whether isolation of pure nuclei using FACS would be beneficial for histone analysis. Fifty post-translationally modified forms were identified in both the in-solution protocol (3S) and the protocol with precipitation (4S). Surprisingly, despite otherwise valid results, we noticed the loss of modified forms of H3 T3–R8.

With the exception of the SP2-purified samples of protocol 3, the variability in the standard deviation of the precursor peak areas within replicates was comparable between all protocols tested (Fig. 3C). Protocols 2 and 3 after SP2 cleanup (3-SP2) provided the lowest median intensities of identified peptides. In particular, median log₂-transformed areas of precursor peaks were as follows: 23.7 (1), 22.2 (2), 24.5 (3), 20 (3-SP2), 23.4 (4), 24.5 (5), 24.4 (3S), and 24.6 (4S), Fig. 3C. Based on the results obtained, protocols 4, 5, 3S, and 4S with the highest number of identified peptidofoms, the highest quality of chromatographic separation, and the highest precursor peak areas were selected for the detailed inspection of the quantitative data.

Fig. 3. Comparison of protocols for histone preparation. A) Number of identified post-translationally modified forms of histone H3.1, H3.3, and H4 peptides is shown. B) Representative chromatograms of monoacetylated N-terminal H4 G4-R17 peptidofoms. Lysines carrying acetylation identified in particular peaks of precursor

ions in the EIC are indicated. Co-elution of positional isomers occurred when Prop was used as a derivatization agent (protocol 1; m/z 768.9465++) while baseline separation was achieved using TMA (825.0091++). Note that the same range of the Y-axis is applied for chromatograms 3, 3S, 4, 4S, and 5, while it was adjusted to a higher or lower range in the case of chromatograms 1 and 2, respectively. C) The technical variability of the quantitative data in each protocol is shown by the mean and standard deviation of the log₂ areas of the histone precursors.

Performance of protocols 4, 5, 3S, and 4S in quantitative terms

The relative abundances of histone peptidofoms were used to compare the quantitative data between the protocols. The dataset of each protocol was evaluated independently, with the internal identification alignment across the raw files based on retention time and m/z . The quantities of histone H3 and H4 peptidofoms were determined from peak areas in EICs. The relative abundances of individual histone peptidofoms were calculated as the ratio of their EIC precursor peak area to the sum of the EIC areas of all forms of the respective peptide sequence.

The relative quantitative data related to histone H4 were the most consistent across the protocols (Fig. 4). The results of all protocols confirmed that the non-modified form of the G4–R17 peptide was highly dominant with a relative abundance of around 90 %. The relative abundance of mono-acetylated forms corresponded to 1–3 %, while the abundance of all multiply acetylated forms was less than 1 %. In histone H3 peptides, dominating forms were non-modified T3–R8 and K18–R26, K9–R17 with K9me₂, and K27–R40 with K27me₁. The higher number of missing values in the histone H3 data across protocols prompted us to check whether these were due to an absence of precursors or missed fragmentation. As mentioned, the absence of post-translationally modified H3 T3–R8 forms was most striking. The complete set of peptides, i.e., unmodified K4, K4ac, K4me₁, K4me₂, and K4me₃, was identified only in protocol 4. Four peptidofoms were identified in protocol 5, with dimethylated lysine missing. Only the unmodified form was detected in the samples prepared from the sorted nuclei (3S and 4S). On the other hand, certain peptidofoms identified in protocols 3S and 4S (e.g., H3K18–R26 with K23me₁ or H3.3K27–R40 with K27me₃) were missing in protocols 4 or 5 (Supplementary Fig. S2). A deeper inspection of the data revealed that the absence of modified forms was often caused by missed fragmentation. Therefore, the respective precursor peaks found in the EIC based on m/z and retention time (hereafter referred to as "MBR" – Match-Between-Runs) were quantified in order to compare the approaches using the complete datasets (Fig. 4 and Supplementary Fig. S2).

A

Relative abundance (including MBR), %					Relative abundance (including MBR), %								
H3 T3–R8					H3.3 K27–R40								
	3S	4	4S	5		3S	4	4S	5				
K4	89.44	86.43	65.44	71.22	K27K36K37	8.82	28.11	7.68	13.22				
K4ac	0.30	0.51	3.28	0.36	K27K36acK37	1.27	1.14	0.81	0.94				
K4me1	7.76	9.25	22.46	21.81	K27K36acK37me3	0.40			0.51				
K4me2	1.64	2.31	5.74	4.19	K27K36me1K37	0.56	1.89	1.08	3.38				
K4me3	0.86	1.50	3.07	2.42	K27K36me2K37	1.64	4.85	2.36	3.77				
H3 K9–R17					H3.3 K27me1K36K37								
	3S	4	4S	5		3S	4	4S	5				
K9K14	3.55	2.71	2.01	2.66	K27me1K36K37ac	0.10		0.13	0.17				
K9K14ac	5.92	1.81	2.72	2.39	K27me1K36acK37	0.88		0.92	1.57				
K9acK14	0.04	0.02	0.05	0.00	K27me1K36me1K37	2.40			1.73				
K9acK14ac	0.21	0.11	0.11	0.07	K27me2K36K37	10.43	17.11	22.15	14.44				
K9me1K14	10.60	7.95	9.96	11.89	K27me2K36acK37	0.51		0.84	0.36				
K9me1K14ac	0.14	0.76	0.38	0.91	K27me3K36K37	2.05	4.49	2.84	3.94				
K9me2K14	77.83	82.90	84.25	78.38	H4 G4–R17								
K9me2K14ac	1.39	3.35	0.20	3.36		3S	4	4S	5				
K9me3K14	0.32	0.35	0.31	0.32	K5K8K12K16	91.76	92.91	88.44	95.60				
K9me3K14ac	0.01	0.04	0.01	0.03	K5K8K12K16ac	1.49	2.51	3.22	1.43				
H3 K18–R26					H4 K5K8K12acK16								
	3S	4	4S	5		3S	4	4S	5				
K18K23	84.50	84.67	81.40	88.93	K5K8K12acK16ac	0.69	0.46	0.88	0.17				
K18K23ac	2.76	2.50	2.43	1.40	K5K8acK12K16	1.79	1.44	2.13	0.95				
K18K23me1	0.02		0.02	0.02	K5K8acK12K16ac	0.29	0.24	0.40	0.12				
K18acK23	10.48	11.33	13.96	8.71	K5K8acK12acK16	0.04	0.04	0.12	0.01				
K18acK23ac	2.19	1.48	2.16	0.91	K5K8acK12acK16ac	0.40	0.19	0.42	0.07				
K18acK23me1	0.02		0.02	0.01	K5acK8K12K16	1.10	1.02	1.40	0.74				
K18me3K23	0.02	0.01		0.02	K5acK8K12K16ac	0.04	0.05	0.16	0.01				
H3.1 K27–R40					H4 K5acK8K12acK16								
	3S	4	4S	5		3S	4	4S	5				
K27K36K37	1.37	3.52	1.38	2.14	K5acK8acK12K16	0.07	0.06	0.13	0.02				
K27K36acK37			0.01	0.01	K5acK8acK12acK16	0.32	0.08	0.12	0.04				
K27K36acK37me3	0.06			0.04	K5acK8acK12K16ac/ K5acK8K12acK16ac	0.05	0.16	0.33	0.03				
K27acK36K37	0.20	0.18	0.30	0.26	K5acK8acK12acK16	0.03	0.02	0.04	0.00				
K27me1K36K37	60.86	55.09	43.60	67.67	K5acK8acK12acK16ac	0.53	0.20	0.43	0.09				
K27me1K36K37ac	0.11	0.25	0.15	0.19	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>N/D</td> <td>0</td> <td>1</td> <td>100</td> </tr> </table>					N/D	0	1	100
N/D	0	1	100										
K27me1S28T32K36acK37	0.04	0.93	0.70	0.79									
K27me1K36me1K37	0.46		0.72	0.50									
K27me2K36K37	35.90	37.98	51.75	26.85									
K27me2K36K37ac	0.06	0.13	0.09	0.07									
K27me2K36acK37	0.00	0.05	0.01	0.02									
K27me3K36K37	0.91	1.87	1.26	1.43									
K27me3K36acK37	0.03		0.03	0.03									

B

Fig. 4. PTMs quantified in histone H3 and H4 peptides prepared by protocols 3S, 4, 4S, and 5. A) Quantitative results with MBR applied. Relative abundance corresponds to the percentage of individual peptidoform peak area of EIC from the sum of the EIC areas of all detected forms of the respective peptide sequence. N/D – Not Detected. For a comparison of quantitative data with and without MBR, see Supplementary Fig. S2. Note

that data without MBR were used for qualitative evaluation in Fig. 3. B). B) Overview of PTMs identified in H3 and H4 N-termini. Comparison of the combinatorial pattern of PTMs detected in protocols 1, 3S, and 5 is depicted in Supplementary Fig. S3.

Discussion

The study of chromatin landscape has become a popular area of biological research because of its direct connection to gene regulation. Although chromatin remodelling mechanisms are widely conserved among eukaryotes, the capacity of plants to adapt to continuously varying environmental conditions suggests higher epigenetic flexibility than in animals²⁴. Next to RNA molecules and DNA methylation, histone sequence variants with their complex and combinatorial character of PTMs provide an efficient regulatory mechanism for maintaining chromosomal structure in the cells (reviewed in²⁵).

Mass spectrometry is particularly helpful in investigating histone's role in chromatin dynamics. Compared to traditional approaches, it allows for the extraction of comprehensive information on the types of histone marks and their positions in amino acid sequences from a single analysis. Importantly, it also enables the detection of combinatorial patterns of PTMs on individual peptides. However, beyond the common challenges of MS-based histone analysis^{10,11,26}, research on plant histones is further complicated by the species-specific chemical composition of plant tissues. This limitation is reflected in the relatively small number of studies addressing plant histone epigenetics²⁷⁻³⁰. It has been shown that the cleanup of plant histone extracts on cut-off membranes coupled with Prop derivatization can serve as a relatively robust and versatile method for a variety of plant tissues, including seedlings, leaves, siliques, and calli of *Arabidopsis thaliana*, leaves of *Solanum lycopersicum*, *Nicotiana benthamiana*, and *Zea mays*³¹. However, the use of Prop represents a limitation regarding insufficient hydrophobicity for chromatographic peak resolution of many histone peptidofoms. The aim of this study was therefore to broaden the applicability of bottom-up histone proteomics in plant research. Notably, the quality and reliability of mass spectrometry data depend on the multi-step workflow involved in histone characterization. In this study, we focused on optimizing histone purity, enzymatic digestion, and chemical derivatization of amine groups to enhance the quality of data obtained by subsequent LC-MS/MS analysis. In this study, we introduced TMA labelling to plant histone preparation workflows before LC-MS/MS, aiming to increase the number of identified and quantified post-translationally modified plant histone forms by enhancing peptidofom hydrophobicity and the resolution of positional isomers. Replacing the Prop with TMA in filter-aided histone preparation yielded a lower number of identified peptidofoms. Conversely, direct derivatization of the histone extract using TMA confirmed the necessity of crude plant histones' cleanup before LC-MS/MS analysis. The strong compositional bias in amino acid content — i.e., the overrepresentation of basic and the underrepresentation of acidic, aromatic, and cysteine residues³² — predetermines the specific behaviour of histone proteins and peptides towards solvents and sorbents used for sample cleanup (Fig. 3). Purification at the protein level appears to be a more reliable approach, as purifying chemically derivatized

histone peptides resulted in substantial selective losses of post-translationally modified forms. The selection of purification methods for proteins and peptides always requires careful consideration, as every extra step potentially decreases the number of identified peptides or their quantity. This is especially problematic for the characterization of histones, where a highly covered sequence is a prerequisite for the identification of histone marks in specific amino acid sites and histone sequence variants based on their unique peptides.

As reported previously, purifying histones from *Arabidopsis* leaves by precipitation leads to problematic re-solubilization, and is not efficient enough, as the samples require further methanol-chloroform cleanup¹⁶. Here, we show that histone re-solubilization is not limiting in general, as the precipitation might serve as a sufficient purification step prior to LC-MS/MS in the case of certain plant species, such as maize. Indeed, precipitation followed by Arg-C Ultra digestion and peptide-level TMA labeling resulted in the detection of a high number of histone peptidofoms, demonstrating that Arg-C Ultra cleavage is advantageous for plant histones. This proves that the preparation of plant histones can be simplified by omitting derivatization at the protein level, analogous to the workflows used for mammalian samples¹².

In-solution derivatization can be performed directly on histones extracted from pure nuclei isolated by FACS, providing a strategy to eliminate tissue-derived compounds interfering with MS and yield higher protein amounts compared to extracts from crude nuclei preparations. This approach offers a viable alternative for histone preparation in cases where the chemical composition of plant tissues affects histone re-solubilization or interferes with chemical derivatization. Overall, FACS-based nuclei purification is a versatile method applicable to all plant species whose cells are prone to lysis and can provide a sufficient amount of tissue for analysis. However, sorting nuclei from small plants or specific organs may be inefficient due to the large number of nuclei required and the associated laboratory and time demands. *Arabidopsis*, for example, is a small plant for which filter-aided histone preparation coupled with Prop-labeling still outperforms protocols that involve nuclei sorting. Another limitation of this otherwise simple method is the requirement for a flow cytometer with sorting capabilities.

To our knowledge, we present a first MS-based approach for profiling histone sequence variants and their PTMs in maize. Compared to *Arabidopsis*²¹, less acetylated histone H4 and a higher percentage of H3K9me2 were detected, suggesting a more compact chromatin structure in maize (Fig. 4). Together with a higher number of histone variants, whose biological roles remain largely unexplored even in *Arabidopsis*, this highlights the vast potential for uncovering mechanisms of chromatin dynamics in crop plants. The study of plant histone epigenetics is currently limited by the availability of methodology, species-specific composition of plant cells, and the amount of available plant material for histone extraction. An improved methodology is required to enable the study of histones across diverse crop species and transfer findings on histone PTMs to plant breeding programs. From this perspective, TMA-based derivatization methods have the potential to advance our understanding of chromatin regulatory mechanisms in crop plants. Based on the protocols tested,

we recommend either precipitation followed by Arg-C Ultra digestion or nuclear sorting followed by in-solution derivatization as the preferred methods for histone analysis in plants. These approaches yield a greater number of peptides with diverse combinatorial PTM patterns compared to the FASP-based procedure (Supplementary Fig. S3). The effectiveness of Arg-C Ultra proteinase supports omitting the protein-level derivatization, and we therefore propose its use as a general replacement of trypsin across protocols.

Supplementary Data

Fig. S1. Total Ion Chromatogram showing a contaminant in the sample prepared by protocol 3.

Fig. S2. Quantitative results of histone H3 and H4 peptides prepared by protocols 3S, 4, 4S, and 5 without (left) and with MBR (right) applied.

Fig. S3. The scheme illustrating the advantages of protocols 3S and 5 over protocol 1, which is currently used for plant histone preparation.

Table S1. Histone sequence variants identified in *Zea mays*.

Author contributions

GL and ZZ conceived and designed the study. MK and JB cultivated the plants and sorted nuclei by FACS. PR and PP performed proteomic experiments and analyzed data. GL, PR, PP, and RP wrote the manuscript. ZZ, MK, and JB revised the manuscript. All authors contributed to the article and approved the submitted version.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Funding

This research was supported by Czech Science Foundation (project No. 25-16290S) and from the project TowArds Next GENERation Crops (CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004581) of the ERDF Pro-gramme Johannes Amos Comenius. CIISB, Instruct-CZ Centre of Instruct-ERIC EU consortium, funded by MEYS CR infrastructure project LM2023042 and European Regional Development Fund-Project "Innovation of Czech Infrastructure for Integrative Structural Biology "(No. CZ.02.01.01/00/23_015/0008175), is gratefully acknowledged for the financial support of the measurements at the CEITEC Proteomics Core Facility. Computational resources were provided by the e-INFRA CZ project (ID:90254), supported by MEYS CR.

Data availability

The pre-print of the article, protocols and the related data have been deposited to Zenodo (doi 10.5281/zenodo.15877680, doi 10.5281/zenodo.15877728 and doi 10.5281/zenodo.15877450).

E-mail addresses of the authors:

Palina Ryzhaya: palina.ryzhaya@ceitec.muni.cz

Pavlna Pírek: pavlna.pirek@ceitec.muni.cz

Radomír Pech: radomir.pech@ceitec.muni.cz

Miroslava Karafiátová: karafiatova@ueb.cas.cz

Jan Bartoš: bartos@ueb.cas.cz

Zbyněk Zdrahal: zdrahal@sci.muni.cz

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